

ASSEMBLY OF STRUCTURES AND WATER DIVIDERS

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Abstract. *In the channels of hydro-reclamation systems, there is often a need to place structures performing various tasks in one place. This arrangement of structures is called a node of structures.*

Keywords: *junction, erosion, vibration, hydromeliorative, tubular, water consumption.*

УЗЕЛ КОНСТРУКЦИЙ И ВОДОДЕЛИТЕЛИ

Аннотация. *В каналах гидромелиоративных систем часто возникает необходимость размещения конструкций, выполняющих различные задачи, в одном месте. Такое расположение структур называется узлом структур.*

Ключевые слова: *соединение, эрозия, вибрация, гидромелиоративное, трубчатое, водопотребление.*

INTRODUCTION

When several structures are placed in one place, it is convenient to manage them, it is easy to organize repair and control, the structures in the node will have less funds for construction. It is advisable to place two or three structures in the node at the junction of the main channel and its networks, as well as channels. If the number of structures located in the node is large, the entrance is extended to the front. In the node of small channels structures, mainly water-receiving regulators are placed, and their number can be five or more. When the number of structures in the node is large, it becomes difficult to place them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this case, a mutual combination of open and tubular regulators is used. In channels in hydromeliorative systems, there are basically two different converging and distancing (figure 1) locations of structures:

When the structures are placed according to the approach scheme (figure1, a) less funds are provided, since the wall for several structures and part of the flutbet is common. In such a location, the structures interact with each other, and their ability to measure water deteriorates. When placed in a distanced scheme, the structures in the node are far apart (figure 1, B). In this case, the structure will improve the ability to measure water, but the funds that go to their construction will increase. A type of water distribution nodes in hydromeliorative channels are water springs. Such structures are installed in places where channels are divided into networks and serve to make the water consumption between them proportional. (Figure 2). According to the mode of operation, water dividers are divided into automatic and controlled types. According to their constructive signs, water dividers appear open and tubular.

Figure 1.

Node of structures in the channel:

a-the approach scheme of the location of the structures; b-the location of the structures divergent scheme; V-structural scheme of the node of structures; 1-incoming Channel; 2-water matchmaking regulator; 3-dimmer structure.

Figure 2.

Water dividers in channels

a, b-open automatic; v-tubular

Outdoor automatic running water springs water consumption networks the incoming channel in the middle is a constant reciprocal given in the calculation operation mode distributes in proportion (figure 2, a,b). Automatic running water one of the disadvantages of burners is that if use if it is necessary to change the water consumption in a given proportion during the period, there will be no possibility of its implementation.

RESULTS

In the event of an accident on the channel, it is impossible to allow any network to be closed on it. In open-controlled water springs, water consumption can be controlled at any time. Open sliders are installed on each network of such water springs. The threshold of the sliders is taken equal to the bottom of the channel on which satxi comes. In the event of an accident in the canal, the zatvors are lowered and the water consumption given to it is increased. All water consumption in the Sungra incoming channel is passed through a regulator installed in the second network. The scheme of the tubular water divider (figure 2, v) is shown.

DISCUSSION

The achievement of such water dividers is that a road can be set up over it for road traffic. One or more rows of pipes can be installed on each network of water dividers, the number of which depends on the water depth and hydraulic mode.

CONCLUSION

The tubular water fountain access head is installed in common for two networks. It is desirable for the purpose of placing pipes in the network as straight A line as possible, but in some cases this cannot be done, their turn is carried out through special blocks. Blocks are made in places from aggregate or concrete. Pipelines water dividers operate in a pressurized and pressure-free mode according to the hydraulic mode.

REFERENCES

1. Hamdamalievich S. A., Nurmuhammad H. Analysis of Heat Transfer of Solar Water Collectors //Middle European Scientific Bulletin. – 2021. – Т. 18. – С. 60-65.
2. Madraximov, M. M., Nurmuxammad, X., & Abdulkhaev, Z. E. (2021, November). Hydraulic Calculation Of Jet Pump Performance Improvement. In International Conference On Multidisciplinary Research And Innovative Technologies (Vol. 2, pp. 20-24).
3. Madaliev, E. U., & qizi Abdukhalilova, S. B. (2022). Repair of Water Networks. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, 3(5), 389-394.
4. Shavkatjon o'g'li, T. B. (2022). SOME INTEGRAL EQUATIONS FOR A MULTIVARIABLE FUNCTION. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(4), 160-163.
5. Усаров, Махаматали Корабоевич, and Гиёсиддин Илхомидинович Маматисаев. "КОЛЕБАНИЯ КОРОБЧАТОЙ КОНСТРУКЦИИ КРУПНОПАНЕЛЬНЫХ ЗДАНИЙ ПРИ ДИНАМИЧЕСКИХ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯХ." Научный форум: технические и физико-математические науки. 2019.Рашидов, Ю. К., Орзиматов, Ж. Т., & Исмоилов, М. М. (2019). Воздушные солнечные коллекторы: перспективы применения в условиях Узбекистана. *ББК 20.1 я43 Э 40*.
6. Akramov, A. A. U., & Nomonov, M. B. U. (2022). Improving the Efficiency Account Hydraulic of Water Supply Sprinklers. Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science, 3(6), 364-370.
7. Madaliev, M. E. U., Maksudov, R. I., Mullaev, I. I., Abdullaev, B. K., & Haidarov, A. R. (2021). Investigation of the Influence of the Computational Grid for Turbulent Flow. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 18, 111-118.
8. Maqsudov, R. I., & qizi Abdukhalilova, S. B. (2021).Improving Support for the Process of the Thermal Convection Process by Installing. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 18, 56-59.
9. ugli Mo'minov, O. A., Maqsudov, R. I., & qizi Abdukhalilova, S. B. (2021). Analysis of Convective Finns to Increase the Efficiency of Radiators used in Heating Systems. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 18, 84-89.
10. Усаров, М. К., and Г. И. Маматисаев. "Вынужденные колебания коробчатой конструкции панельных зданий при динамических воздействиях." Проблемы механики 2 (2010): 23-25.

11. Nosirov A.A., Nasirov I.A. Simulation of Spatial Own of Vibrations of Axisymmetric Structures EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF MODERN SCIENCE <https://emjms.academicjournal.io>
12. Shavkatjon o'g'li, T. B. (2022). Proving The Inequalities Using a Definite Integral and Series. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 13, 64-68.
13. Rashidov, Y. K., & Ramankulov, S. A. (2021). Improving the Efficiency of Flat Solar Collectors in Heat Supply Systems. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, 2(12), 152-159
14. Malikov, Z. M., & Madaliev, E. U. (2019). Mathematical simulation of the speeds of ideally newtonovsky, incompressible, viscous liquid on a curvilinearly smoothed pipe site. Scientific-technical journal, 22(3), 64-73.
15. Сатторов, А. Х., Акрамов, А. А. У., & Абдуразаков, А. М. (2020). Повышение эффективности калорифера, используемого в системе вентиляции. Достижения науки и образования, (5 (59)), 9-12.
16. Abobakirovich, A. B., Sodikovich, A. Y., & Ogli, M. I. I. (2019). Optimization of operating parameters of flat solar air heaters. Вестник науки и образования, (19-2 (73)), 6-9.
17. Usmonova, N. A. (2021). Structural Characteristics of the Cavern at a Fine Bubbled Stage of Cavitation. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 18, 95-101.
18. Abdukarimov, B. A., O'tbosarov, S. R., & Tursunaliyev, M. M. (2014). Increasing Performance Efficiency by Investigating the Surface of the Solar Air Heater Collector. NM Safarov and A. Alinazarov. Use of environmentally friendly energy sources.
19. Nasirov Ismail Azizovich. On The Accuracy of the Finite Element Method on the Example of Problems about Natural Oscillations. EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF MODERN SCIENCE <https://emjms.academicjournal.io>
20. Мадхадимов, М. М., Абдулхаев, З. Э., & Сатторов, А. Х. (2018). Регулирования работы центробежных насосов с изменением частота вращения. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (12-1), 83-88
21. Abdullayev, B. X., & Rahmankulov, S. A. (2021). Modeling Aeration in High Pressure Hydraulic Circulation. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, 2(12), 127-136.
22. Abbasov, Y. S., & ugli Usmonov, M. A. (2022). Design of an Effective Heating System for Residential and Public Buildings. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES, 3(5), 341-346.
23. Умурзакова, М. А., Усмонов, М. А., & Рахимов, М. Н. (2021). АНАЛОГИЯ РЕЙНОЛЬДСА ПРИ ТЕЧЕНИЯХ В ДИФФУЗОРНО-КОНФУЗОРНЫХ КАНАЛАХ. Экономика и социум, (3-2), 479-486.
24. Мо'minov, O. A. O'tbosarov Sh. R. "Theoretical analysis of the ventilation emitters used in low-temperature heat supply systems, and heat production of these emitters" Eurasian journal of academic research, 495-497.
25. Hamdamalievich S. A. Determination of the deposition of particles contained in the water passing through the sump well //Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 244-251.

26. Nosirov A.A., Nasirov I.A. Simulation of Spatial Own of Vibrations of Axisymmetric Structures EUROPEAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF MODERN SCIENCE <https://emjms.academicjournal.io>
27. Usmonova, N. A., & Khudaykulov, S. I. (2021, April). SPATIAL CAVERNS IN FLOWS WITH THEIR PERTURBATIONS IMPACT ON THE SAFETY OF THE KARKIDON RESERVOIR. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 126-130)
28. Хамдамалиевич, S. A., & Rahmankulov, S. A. (2021, July). Investigation of heat transfer processes of solar water, air contact collector. In E-Conference Globe (pp. 161-165)
29. Madaliev, M. E. U., Rakhmankulov, S. A., & Tursunaliyev, M. M. U. (2021). Comparison of Finite-Difference Schemes for the Burgers Problem. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 18, 76-83
30. Рашидов, Ю. К., Орзиматов, Ж. Т., Эсонов, О. О. Ў., & Зайнабидинова, М. И. К. (2022). СОЛНЕЧНЫЙ ВОЗДУХОНАГРЕВАТЕЛЬ С ВОЗДУХОПРОНИЦАЕМЫМ МАТРИЧНЫМ АБСОРБЕРОМ. Scientific progress, 3(4), 1237-1244.